

Speculation on 2-Slit Interference- Photon Passes Through One Slit but Impacts the Other?

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In classical physics, the notion of probability may arise from a lack of knowledge by one observer, while a second observer may have the required knowledge to eliminate probability. For example, when a coin is tossed, observer 1 may not see the outcome and so considers probability, while observer 2 sees the outcome and does not use probability.

If one applies these ideas to 2-slit interference, then one has a problem which shows that quantum mechanics is not the same as classical probabilistic theory. Observer 1 may not measure the slit through which a photon passes and would then argue for probability. If observer 2, however, tries to measure through which slit the photon passes, by measuring space outside of the 2-slit apparatus, then interference is broken. In a previous note (1), we suggested that 2-slit interference involves an entangled state of probabilities from each slit.

Here we suggest that a photon can only pass through slit regions, meaning that a photon can interact with the molecules in the slit apparatus and impart an impulse. We suggest that instead of measuring through which slit a photon passes, outside of the 2-slit apparatus, one could imagine tiny detectors within the material of the 2-slit apparatus which could determine where an impulse was imparted. The question then is: Does this mean one would know through which slit the photon passed? We argue that it would not because one would then have a non-interference situation. The incoming photon moves along a ray, but after interacting with the 2-slit apparatus, one has an entangled probability state which considers both slits, which means that one cannot know which slit the photon passed through and have interference. This then suggests that an impulse hit to the left slit does not necessarily mean that the photon passes through the left slit. The trajectory (constant velocity c) is not the same as the momentum hit strike probability we suggest. The interference pattern, we suggest, is based on the impulse hit probability ($\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_1) + \exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_2)$) which forms a pattern in x - y space regardless of the actual path the photon takes.

Classical Probability and Information

Classical probability may arise due to a lack of information, but this is based on the observer. A coin may be tossed. Observer 1 does not see the outcome and so describes it using probability and argues there is entropy. Observer 2 sees the outcome and does not assign any probability or entropy. The question then becomes: Does quantum mechanics also behave in the same manner given that it is a probabilistic theory? We argue that the answer is no, at least in the 2-slit interference case.

2-Slit Interference Situation

The 2-Slit Interference problem involves a photon (or particle) passing through one slit or the other, but there is something else occurring which is not present in classical mechanics. In particular, interference only occurs if the slits are about \hbar/p apart. This suggests that there is

a link between momentum and space which is nonclassical. Classically, one thinks of a photon trajectory, with the photon being a point and delivering a p (vector) impulse at this same point. This cannot be the quantum picture, because otherwise a photon would pass through one slit or the other and only interact with the slit through which it passed, if it interacted at all. Classically, one thinks of a definite trajectory with impulse hits at the point of the particle. Quantum mechanically if the particle travels along a ray with constant speed, its trajectory is classical $x=vt$, but its impulse behaviour need not be. In other words, the impulse hit does not necessarily localize the particle at that x point.

Instead we suggest an entangled probability state based on both slits, and a second probability mechanism based on p and x . The first probability situation is one related to whether the photon passed through one slit or the other.

As a result, only asking the classical question: Through which slit did the photon pass? means that one is ignoring the second probability mechanism, namely the p - x probability manifested through $\exp(ipx)$ and arising from special relativity (as we have argued in (1)). If one tries to measure through which slit the photon passed, like observer 2 measuring the result of a coin flip, one can determine the slit (by localizing the photo), but the interference pattern is broken. Thus, the second probability mechanism is destroyed by such a measurement taken outside of the 2-slit apparatus. This suggests that interference is based on non-classical probability thinking, i.e. a second kind of probability, namely x - p , $\exp(ipx)$ probability.

Now, a photon can only pass through the slit regions. This suggests that a photon interacts with molecules in the slit apparatus and can deliver an impulse hit. Even if the photon passes through a slit, impulse hits seem to be delivered, otherwise the photon should pass through in a vertical direction to the slit apparatus, which does not happen (as measured in the interference pattern on a screen). We suggest that one could place tiny detectors within the solid region of the 2-slit apparatus and determine roughly where an impulse occurs. We suggest, however, that this does not mean that one knows through which slit the photon passed. If one did know, then one would simply draw a single ray from that slit to the point on the screen and there would be no interference. This suggests then that even knowing the location of an impulse hit by the photon, does not show its trajectory, because impulse hits are probabilistic in space ($\exp(ipx)$). A photon might deliver a hit to the left slit and yet pass through the right. This means that one cannot determine through which slit the photon passed and must create an x - y space probability pattern based on:

$$\exp(ip \cdot r_1) + \exp(ip \cdot r_2) \quad ((1))$$

In other words, there is an interference or entangled state involving the 2-slits and one cannot describe this as a product state of $|\text{slit } 1\rangle|\text{slit } 2\rangle$ as in classical physics. Rather one has $|\text{slit } 1 \text{ slit } 2\rangle$, an entangled state regardless of where the impulse hit was delivered. If one measures the location of the photon outside the 2-slit apparatus, it seems one breaks the entangled state in the following manner. Detecting the photon means interacting with it, i.e. its momentum. We suggest that in general the presence of an impulse hit does not determine the location of the photon, but in this measurement, detecting the photon localizes it, breaking the entangled state. In the case of 2-slits, an interaction with one slit does not localize the photon, it can still pass

through the other. Thus, it seems that one does not use a second 2-slit apparatus to determine through which slit the photon passed.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that 2-slit interference is not simply about asking through which slit a photon passes. The fact that interference only occurs when the slits are about \hbar/p apart suggests that there exists an x - p probability in space which does not exist classically, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, one has probability in x - y for p hits by a photon. This implies that a photon could deliver a momentum impulse hit to the left slit, but still pass through the right. The 2-slit mechanism creates an entangled probability state involving both slits ((1))., we suggest This pattern determines high and low probability paths for the photon. If one tries to make a measurement outside the 2-slit apparatus which localizes the photon, then the entangled state is broken and the photon is sent along a single ray and there is no interference. There seems to be still a phase along this ray, but no there is no longer probability over x - y space given by ((1))

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Two Probabilities in Quantum Mechanics, One Constraining the Other? (preprint, zenodo, 2024)